

A method for screening rice cultivars for cold tolerance at early seedling stage

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In temperate areas, high-elevation areas, or some newly-cultivated tropic areas, low temperatures may kill, retard, or weaken the growth of pregerminated seeds.

This method is proposed to test cold tolerance of rice cultivars at the early seedling stage.

For each rice to be screened, put 20 germinated seeds in each of 3 vials or small bottles lined with moistened tissue paper. When seedlings have a coleoptile of 5 mm, subject to 4°C cold treatment for 10 days. Allow the seedlings to recover for 10 days at ambient temperature in a greenhouse. Then, score for cold tolerance at early seedling stage (see

Score	Vigor	Criteria
		Density
1	Seedling height more than 10 cm, green leaves.	All seedlings alive.
3	Seedling height generally 8-10 cm,	Less than 30% seedlings dead.
5	Seedling height generally 5-7 cm,	30-50% seedlings dead.
7	Seedling height generally 3-4 cm,	More than 50% seedlings dead.
9	All seedlings dead, seedling height < 1 cm.	All seedlings dead.

chart).

The reactions of germinated seeds to cold treatment vary considerably with stage of development. Discrimination between cold-tolerant and susceptible cultivars is more obvious if seeds subjected to cold treatment have a well-developed coleoptile of about 5 mm and traces of chlorophyll. Less-developed seedling of a susceptible rice could show little effect of the cold treatment and be mistaken for a tolerant cultivar.

Rices also differ in developmental habits. Generally, most indicas reach the optimum stage of development after 72 hours of incubation. Japonica varieties take longer. It is advisable to divide a

collection according to the rates of development of the types and subject seedlings to cold treatment only when they have arrived at the correct stage.

To prevent drying of the seedlings, check moisture content of the vials regularly. Include a fungicide in first watering to avoid fungus damage.

Score samples for both seedling vigor and density of surviving plants and take the mean of the two scores.

With this method, Barkat (K78-13), Baekgogna, and Jo Do were found tolerant (score 1 to 3) at the early seedling stage; Taichung Sen Yu 229, Dumai, Suweon 287, and IR8 were sensitive (5 to 9). ■

Rice pollination characteristics related to high temperature tolerance

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High temperature-induced sterility has not been an important problem in traditional cropping patterns. However, with the development of irrigation systems for dry season cropping of rice and the

expansion of rice production in semiarid countries, high temperature tolerance may become an important breeding objective. Several rice cultivars and breeding lines differing in reaction to high temperature at the anthesis stage were studied for their ability to shed pollen on the stigma.

Spikelets of each variety or line were collected in the afternoon of the day of anthesis. The number of pollen grains

on the stigma was counted and stigmas with more than 100 pollen grains were scored as 100. Plants from the 29°/21° and 38°/27°C glasshouse rooms of the IRRI phytotron and from the field at IRRI were sampled in the 1980 dry season and the 1981 wet season. Percentage of fertility or filled grains was measured on plants grown in the phytotron. The number of pollen grains per anther was measured on plants growing in the field.

Percent fertility, pollen grains per stigma, and pollen grains per anther for 6 rices grown in the phytotron and in the field at IRRI, 1980 wet season and 1981 dry season.

Variety or line	Phytotron				Field		
	Fertility (%)		Pollen grains (no./stigma)		Pollen grains (no./stigma)		Pollen grains (no./anther),
	29°/21°C ^a	38°/21°C	29°/21°C	38°/27°C	1980 WS	1981%	1981 DS
<i>Heat tolerant</i>							
N22	88.9 bc	30.0 ab	65.4 b	65.6 a	<i>b</i>	85.7 a	1085 b
IR2006-P12-12-2-2	97.9 a	31.8 a	84.9 a	68.2 a	86.8 a	80.8 a	1908 a
IET4658 (UPR96-1-1-1)	88.1 bc	19.5 bc	66.3 b	63.0 a	76.8 a	72.9 a	1255 b
<i>Heat susceptible</i>							
IR28	71.4 d	3.6 d	33.1 c	12.5 b	60.9 b	70.7 a	1800 a
IR1561-228-3-3	94.8 ab	4.3 d	32.6 c	19.6 b	54.0 bc	40.8 b	1705 a
IR52	84.1 cd	3.1 d	17.3 c	1.8 b	42.4 c	38.2 b	1750 a

^aWithin a column means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bNo measurement was made for N22 in the wet season of 1980.